

**GRAMMATICAL CATEGORIES OF ADJECTIVE: COMPARATIVE
ADJECTIVES OF UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES**

Shamuratova Muhayyo Muzaffar qizi

Student at Navoi State Pedagogical Institute, Uzbekistan

Annotation: This thesis delves into a comparative study of the grammatical category of comparative adjectives in Uzbek and English languages, focusing on their structural properties, syntactic functions, and semantic implications. By analyzing the distinct characteristics and usage patterns of comparative adjectives in both languages, this research aims to provide valuable insights into the cross-linguistic variations and similarities and differences in the usage of these adjectival forms.

Keywords: Adjective, comparative, grammatical category

Annotatsiya: Bu tezisda o'zbek va ingliz tillaridagi qiyosiy sifatlarning grammatik kategoriyasini qiyosiy tadqiq qilish, ularning tuzilish xususiyatlari, sintaktik vazifalari va semantik ma'nolariga e'tibor qaratiladi. Har ikki tildagi qiyosiy sifatlarning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari va qo'llanish usullarini tahlil qilib, ushbu tadqiqot sifat shakllarining qo'llanilishidagi tillararo o'zgarishlar va o'xshashliklar haqida qimmatli tushunchalar berishga qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar:

INTRODUCTION

Adjectives are one of the most important parts of speech in the English language. They are used to describe people, places, things, and ideas. Adjectives can make a sentence more interesting and can provide more information about the nouns they modify. Different grammars in languages from the point of view of general linguistics meanings are found. But these grammatical meanings and their

expression styles are common and not the same for all languages. Each language has its own grammatical meanings and ways of expressing them. They are not in individual cases, but according to the closeness of the types of meaning occurs in groups. In such groups, they should be at least two or more. That's conjunctions are a grammatical category in the literature on linguistics is held as Grammatical category types. Grammatical categories are of three types according to the way of expression divided into:

- 1) synthetic grammatical categories;
- 2) analytical grammatical categories;
- 3) mixed grammatical category or synthetic-analytical grammar categories.

Analytical grammatical categories are expressed only by auxiliary words.

If in forming the levels of the polysyllabic adjective in English if we accept the words “*more*” and “*most*” as auxiliary words, as some scholars say, then the qualitative (polysyllabic) level category is pure analytical tool will be made with:

interesting — more interesting - the most interesting

attractive - more attractive - the most attractive.[1;68-69-70].

A comparative adjective is utilized to draw a comparison between two individuals or objects. It is employed to indicate that one entity exhibits a greater degree of a particular trait or excels in a quality compared to another. Examples of comparative adjectives include words like “*taller*”, “*smarter*” and “*slower*”.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. *There was always another blockbuster case on the horizon that was **bigger than the last.***[The Monk;15]

*Mag'lubiyatni ko'p ko'rgan odamga xatar goho aslidan **kattaroq** ko'rinur.*

[Yulduzli;175]

In the taken examples for comparison, we can see the differences and similarities of the comparative adjectives in the two languages. For example; in English we use –

er, (-r if adjective already ends with e) with one syllabic, gradeable adjective and in Uzbek -roq suffix to make comparative adjective. In addition, when comparing one thing to another in English, the word "than" is used referring to the two people or thing, while in Uzbek, it is made by adding -dan (chiqish kelishigi) to the noun. As we can see, the construction of the comparative degree in this way is very close to each other in both languages.

2. *I was so much **more perceptive** than the others at the firm...* [Monk;14]

*Sizdan ko'ra qizingiz **aqlliroq**.* [Yulduzli;140]

In English, we use the quantifier *more* before the adjective if the adjective is polysyllabic. But, in Uzbek, the suffix -roq is applied to only qualitative adjectives, regardless of syllable.

*Do you want to be a **better** father and live a more balanced, rewarding life?* [Monk;65]

*Nigor xonimdan ko'ra o'zining ahvoli **yaxshiroq** ekanini namoyish qilmoqchi edi.* [Yulduzli;14]

The adjective in this example is irregular, which changes its form in the comparative degree, *better* is the comparative form of *good*. In Uzbek language that kind of adjectives do not exist. In English, such adjectives do not include a large group.

- Bad-worse
- Far-further (farther)
- Little-less
- Much-more

CONCLUSION

The comparative structures in English and Uzbek exhibit unique patterns and rules, reflecting the linguistic diversity and nuances of each language. While English includes irregular adjectives with distinct comparative forms, Uzbek maintains consistency with the use of "-roq" for qualitative comparisons. Understanding these

differences enhances language comprehension and cross-cultural communication.

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